

PHYSICO CHEMICAL PARAMETERS OF SOME ABANDONED TIN MINE PONDS IN JOS AND ENVIRONS AND THEIR SUITABILITY FOR FISH FARMING IN PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Mining activities have been linked to the release of heavy metals into aquatic environments, which can cause ecosystem poisoning, fish kills, disease outbreaks, and contamination of the food chain. Such contamination may also result in human diseases like cancer, organ damage, and enzyme suppression. The main aim was to determine the physicochemical parameters of the mine pond water and the suitability of the ponds for fish farming, standard methods of Association of Analytical Chemists and American Public Health Association were used. Portable laboratory sample testing instrument (e.g., pH meter, thermometer, turbidimeter, spectrophotometer, lovibond comperator 1000) were used for determination and analysis. Notably, the following parameters were determined in varying concentrations across the ponds. Water temperature ranges from 19.5 - 23.0 °C, colour ranges from 6.0 - 7.6 Hz, pH ranged from 6.8 - 7.5, EC ranges from 173 - 432 $\mu\text{s}/\text{cm}$, TDS

ranges from 169- 597mg/dm³, total alkalinity ranges from 24.00 - 85.0 mg/dm³, dissolved oxygen ranged from 6.4 - 13.2mg/dm³, BOD ranges from 1.1 - 4.5 mg/dm³, total hardness ranges 98.75 – 298.7 mg/dm³. The study showed that the physicochemical parameters of the ponds are favorable for the survival of Catfish. Control sources of contamination and refuse dumping at pond sites, implement erosion control to reduce ions metal-laden runoff into ponds.

KEYWORDS: Mine pond, physico-chemical parameters, contamination.

INTRODUCTION

Ponds are defined as small, shallow lentic ecosystems, typically less than 2–10 hectares in surface area and shallow enough (<3–6 meters) for sunlight to penetrate to the benthos across most of their extent.^[1,2] This distinguishes them from lakes, which often exhibit persistent thermal stratification, and rivers, which are lotic. Ponds are dynamic systems with high ecological variability, driven by their small volume and high perimeter-to-area ratio, which amplifies terrestrial-aquatic interactions.^[3] Research emphasizes their role as biogeochemical hotspots, processing carbon, nitrogen, and phosphorus at rates disproportionate to their size.^[4]

Ecologically, ponds support diverse communities of phytoplankton, zooplankton, macrophytes, macroinvertebrates, and vertebrates with biodiversity often exceeding that of larger water bodies per unit area.^[5] Studies in Hydrobiologia classify them by origin (natural vs. artificial), hydroperiod (permanent, seasonal, or ephemeral), and function (e.g., carbon sinks, biodiversity reservoirs).^[6] Ponds are also framed as experimental systems for testing ecological theory, such as meta community dynamics or trophic cascades. Ponds are globally distributed across all climatic zones, with an estimated 304 million worldwide, accounting for ~30% of standing water surface area. Their locations are mapped using remote sensing and field surveys, revealing distinct regional patterns.^[3]

Abandoned mine ponds are remnants of historical mining activities, they are prevalent globally and pose significant environmental and health risks due to heavy metal contamination. These water bodies, often formed in excavated pits or tailings impoundments, accumulate metals such as lead (Pb), cadmium (Cd), arsenic (As), zinc (Zn), and copper (Cu), which can leach into surrounding soils and water systems. With increasing pressure to repurpose degraded lands for agriculture in resource-scarce regions, assessing the risks associated with heavy metals in these ponds and their suitability for farming has become critical.

Mining Ponds

Mining ponds are artificial water bodies created as part of mining operations to manage water, waste, or extracted materials. They are integral to mineral extraction and processing, serving various purposes depending on the mining method and stage. Broadly, they fall into categories like tailings ponds, process ponds, and settling ponds. Tailings ponds, the most

common type, store slurry which is a mixture of water, fine-grained waste rock (tailings), and residual chemicals left after ore processing.^[7] Process ponds hold Pregnant Leach Solutions (PLS) or barren solutions during heap leaching, facilitating metal extraction (e.g., gold, copper).^[8] Settling or clarification ponds allow solids to separate from water, often for recycling or discharge.^[9]

Mining ponds are studied as engineered systems with complex geochemical and hydrological dynamics. Tailings ponds, for instance, are hotspots for heavy metal mobilization due to sulfide oxidation, producing acid mine drainage (AMD) with pH as low as 2–4.^[10] Their design often using earthen dams liners, aims to contain toxic effluents, but failures highlight their environmental risk.^[11] Research in Journal of Cleaner Production explores their role in water management, emphasizing liners (e.g., geo membranes) to prevent seepage.^[12]

Mining ponds are located globally wherever mining occurs, tied to geological deposits and extraction activities. Their distribution reflects the prevalence of metal ore, coal, and industrial mineral mines.^[13]

AIM AND OBJECTIVE OF THE RESEARCH

The aim of the research was to determine the physico-chemical parameters of some abandoned tin mine ponds in Jos and environs and their suitability for fish farming. The specific objective was to determine the physicochemical parameters of the water in the selected mine ponds.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Equipment

Analytical balance, Mattler Company Ltd, Laboratory Oven, Hot Plate/Magnetic Stirrer (Gallenkanp Ltd), Muffle Furnace (Carbolite Company Ltd), Conductivity Meter (HANNA Company Ltd), Turbidimeter HACH 2100N (HACH Company Ltd), pH meter pH51, Milwaukee (Milwaukee, Company Ltd), Lovibond 1000 Comparator (Lovibond Company Ltd), Flame Photometer (Fison Scientific Equipment Company Ltd), Spectrophotometer UV/visible (JENWAY Company Ltd), Atomic Absorption spectrophotometer Agilent (Agilent company Ltd), HANNA equipment for water analysis (HANNA Equipment Company Ltd, United Kingdom).

Apparatus

Crucibles (Ceramic Company Ltd), Porcelaine Evaporating Dish (Ceramic Company Ltd), Separating Glass Funnel, Conical Flask, Graduated Measuring, Graduated Pipettes, Burettes, Beakers, Sample Tubes, Reagent Bottles, Volumetric Flask and Digestion Flask (Jobling Company Ltd, United Kingdom). Sieve 0.2 ug (Stainless Steel Company Ltd), Gouch Glass Filter Cone (Corning Laboratory Ltd), Thermometer (Quick fit Company Ltd), Water distiller (Manesty Steel Company, Ltd). United Kingdom.

Trowell (Lion Head Company Ltd), PVC tubes (Tiger Company Ltd), Polyethylene bottles, gallons (Ok Plastic Ltd). Teflown plastic containers (Ok Plastic Ltd), Plastic pipe (Tiger Company Ltd), Plastic Gallons (Leo Plastic Industry Ltd). Nigeria.

Reagents

Nitric acid, Perchloric Acid, Sodium chloride, Sulphuric acid, Potassium Chromate, Silver Nitrate, Ammonium Pyrrolidine Dithiocarbamate, Tin(II) Chloride, Manganous sulphate, Sodiumthiosulphate, Ammonium molybdate, Potassium Iodide, Urea, Calcium Carbonate, Ethylinediamintetracetic acid, Sodium Dihydrogen Phosphate, Disodium Hydrogen Phosphate, Phenolphthalein, Methyl Orange, Silver nitrate, Erichrom blackT, Triethanolamine, Absolute Ethanol, Lead Nitrate, Zinc Chloride, Barium Chloride, Sodium Thiosulphate. All from British Drug House company Ltd, United Kingdom. Methyl Isobutyl Ketone, Sodium Azide, Perchloric acid, Hydrochloric acid, Acetic acid, Glycerol, Potassium Iodide. Foison Chemicals Ltd and Sodium Hydroxide (May & Beaker).

All the reagents used for this research are of analytical grade, obtained from Analar reagents and chemicals, (British Drug House, Foison, May & Beaker, Company Ltd, United Kingdom).

STUDY AREA

Plateau State is located in the North Central zone of Nigeria. And is located between latitude 8°24' N and 10°30'N and longitudes 8°32' E and 10°38'E (Figure 1). The state was named after the picture square Jos Plateau, a mountainous area in the north of the state with a captivating rock formation. Bare rocks are scattered across the grasslands which covers the Plateau. The altitude ranges from 1,200 meters (3,900 ft) to a peak of 1,829 meters (6,001 ft) above sea level at the Shere Hills. Years of tin and columbite mining have left the area strewn with deep gorges and ponds. Plateau State, though situated in the tropical zone, a higher

altitude means that Plateau State has a near temperate climate, with an average temperature of between 13-22 °C. Harmattan winds cause the coldest weather between December and February. The warmest temperatures usually occur in the dry season months of March and April. The mean annual rainfall varies between 131.75 cm (52 in) and 146 cm (57 in) on the Plateau. The highest rainfall is recorded during the wet season months of July and August.^[14] The sampled area and points were identified by the use of GPS device and Google Earth. These were measured at the specific sampled points, ground thru-thing as can be seen on the maps.

Sampling Site Features and Environment. It is obvious that open space and heaps of rocks, sand and wastes, are common features of mining areas in Nigeria. In Plateau State, tin and columbite mining holes and heaps of sand and debris produced by the opencast method of mining, gave rise to accelerated erosion and flooding among many Effects.^[13] The situation is not different from the surroundings of the environment of the ponds sampled in Plateau. Gurum, Haske and Zawan ponds, had buildings, farm lands and gutter channeled into them. The surrounding soil was clay-loamy, Laterite soil and sedimentary rocks.

Figure 1. Map of Nigeria Showing Plateau State.

Figure 2.: Map of Plateau State showing the four Local Government Areas of Study.

Figure 3: Sampled Ponds.
Source: GIS.

Plate 1: Gurum Ponds.

Plate 2: Haske Ponds.

Plate 3: Zawan Ponds.

SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Random sampling technique was used for the sampling of the ponds.

- i. Sampled media (Pond water,)
- ii. Standard analytical procedures from Association of Analytical Chemist,^[15] American Public Health Association^[16] & Environmental Protection Agency.^[17]

METHODS

Standard methods of Association of Analytical Chemist^[15] and standard methods from American Public Health Association^[18] was used for the analysis.

Sample collection

The samples were collected at the sampling sites and locations on Figure 2 and Figure 3.

1. Water sample collection

Pond water samples were collected from the respective mine ponds monthly for twelve months in 2021, covering dry and rainy season into clean 4 litres plastic bottles and gallons. The samples were kept in the refrigerator at 4°C for physicochemical analysis.

2. Preservation of water samples

The samples for physicochemical parameters were determined immediately and some kept in the refrigerator at 4°C for further analysis.

Preparation of some reagents

NaOH solution (0.02 M) was prepared by weighing 0.8 g NaOH and dissolving it in distilled water in a 1dm³ flask while the volume was made to the mark.

i) Eriochrom Black T. solution

Eriochrom black T. indicator: 0.2 g of Eriochrom black T. indicator was dissolved in a mixture of 15 cm³ triethanolamine and 5 cm³ absolute Ethanol.

ii) Buffer solution pH10

Buffer solution of pH10: 16.9 g of ammonium chloride was dissolved in 143 cm³ concentrated ammonium hydroxide and was diluted to 250 cm³ with distilled water.

iii) Standard EDTA solution

Standard EDTA 0.01M: 3.723 g of EDTA salt was dissolved in deionized water and was diluted to 1000 cm³ in a volumetric flask.

iv) Standard calcium solution

Standard calcium solution: 1000 mg (1 g) anhydrous CaCO₃ was dissolved in 500 cm³ conical flask 1:1 HCl was added to the flask and swirled until it dissolved completely. 3M NH₄OH was added to the flask and was adjusted with dil. HCl as necessary it was made up to mark in a 1 dm³ flask. 1 cm³ of the solution contains 1 mg CaCO₃.

Determination of Acidity

NaOH 0.02M solution was prepared by weighing 0.8 g NaOH and dissolving it in distilled water into a 1dm³ flask. The distilled water was boiled for 10minutes to expel carbon-dioxide (CO₂) 50 cm³ of mine-pond water sample was pipetted and transferred into a conical flask and 3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator was added. The content of the conical flask was titrated with 0.02M NaOH. (Sodium hydroxide) from a burette until the 1st permanent pink colour appears and the titre volume was recorded. Total acidity was determined using:

$$\text{Total acidity as CO}_2 \text{ in mg/dm}^3 = \frac{M \times V_1 \times 1000}{V_2}$$

Where: M = Molarity of the Alkali

V₁= Titre volume of the Alkali

V₂= Volume of the sample used

Determination of Alkalinity

Phenolphthalein Alkalinity: Mine pond water sample, 50 cm³ of the water sample was measured into a conical flask and 3 drops of phenolphthalein indicator were added. There

was no colour change with the indicator. The titre was recorded as zero (0) for phenolphthalein end-point volume.

Methyl Orange Alkalinity: Mine pond water sample, 50 cm³ was measured into a conical flask and 3 drops of methyl orange indicator were added to the sample in each flask, the solution became yellow and was titrated with 0.01M H₂SO₄ acid until the colour changed to pink and the titre was recorded as methyl-orange end-point volume.

Total alkalinity was determined using

$$\text{Total alkalinity as (mg/dm}^3\text{) CaCO}_3 = \frac{V \times M \times 100 \times 1000}{\text{Vol. of sample}}$$

where: M = molarity of acid used

V = total volume of acid used

100 = molar mass of CaCO₃ in (g)

1000 = conversion to mg/dm³

Determination of Dissolved Solids

Clean porcelain crucibles were heated on a hot plate for 30 minutes. The crucibles were cooled in a desiccator for 10 minutes and then weighed carefully on the analytical balance and the weight recorded. 50 cm³ of water samples were measured into respective porcelain crucibles and evaporated to dryness on a hot plate. The crucibles were cooled for 10 minutes in the desiccator and reweighed. Triplicate operations were carried out for each sample.

Total dissolved solids was determined using

$$\text{Total dissolved Solid (mg/dm}^3\text{)} = \frac{(B-A) \times 1000}{\text{Vol.of Sample Used}}$$

where A = Weight of empty crucible in gram

 B = Weight of crucible and dissolved solids

Vol. of Sample Used= 50 cm³

Determination of Chloride

Mine pond water sample 50 cm³ was pipetted into a conical flask and 1 cm³ of 5% potassium chromate indicator was added. The flask was continuously swirled and the solution titrated with 0.1M Silver Nitrate solution until a brick red end-point was reached. The burette readings (titre value) were noted. Indicator blank titration was determined by adding 1cm³ of 5% potassium chromate (K₂CrO₄) to 50 cm³ of deionized water and was titrated with the

0.1M AgNO₃ from the burette this was deduced from all the chloride titration values. The titrations were done in triplicates.

Total chloride concentration was determined using

$$\text{mg/dm}^3\text{Cl} = \frac{(\text{Titre Vol. of AgNO}_3 - \text{Blank}) \times \text{Molarity of AgNO}_3 \times 35.5 \times 1000}{\text{Cm}^3 \text{ of Sample Used}}$$

Determination of Total Hardness

Mine pond water sample 50 cm³ was pipetted into 3 conical flasks respectively, and was added 1cm³ of buffer solution. It was swirled and added 3 drops of indicator. The solution was titrated with 0.01M EDTA solution until colour changed from red-wine to blue. The EDTA was also standardized against standard calcium solution using 10cm³ portions to check the EDTA solution before use.

Total hardness was determined using the formula below

$$\text{Total Hardness (mg/dm}^3\text{) CaCO}_3 = \frac{V_{\text{EDTA}} \times M_{\text{EDTA}} \times 100 \times 1000}{\text{cm}^3 \text{ of sample}}$$

where

V _{EDTA}	=	Titre Volume of EDTA used
M _{EDTA}	=	Molar Concentration of EDTA
100	=	Molar Mass of CaCO ₃
1000	=	Conversion Factor to mg/dm ³
Cm ³	=	Volume of Sample used

Determination of Calcium Hardness

The pond water sample 50 cm³, was pipetted into a 250 cm³ conical flask. 2 cm³ of Ammonia/Ammonium chloride buffer solution of pH10, was added into the conical flask. 3 drops of Eriochrome black T indicator were added into the conical flask, using glass dropper pipette. The content of the conical flask was immediately titrated with a 0.01M EDTA solution mixing continuously until the colour change from red wine colour to blue.

Calcium hardness concentration was determined using the formula below

$$\text{CaCO}_3 \text{ (mg/dm}^3\text{)} = \frac{40.08 \times V_{\text{EDTA}} \times M_{\text{EDTA}} \times 1000}{\text{cm}^3 \text{ of sample}}$$

where

V _{EDTA}	=	Volume of 0.01m EDTA used as titre
M _{EDTA}	=	Concentration of EDTA (0.01)
40.08	=	Molar Mass of Calcium

$$1000 = \text{conversion factor to milligram}$$

$$\text{Cm}^3 \text{ of sample} = \text{Volume of sample used (50cm}^3\text{)}$$

Determination of Magnesium Concentration

Mine pond water sample 50 cm³ was pipetted into a 250 cm³ conical flask, 2 cm³ of Ammonia/Ammonium chloride buffer was added into the conical flask. 3 drops of Eriochrome black T indicator was added into the conical flask, using glass dropper. The content of the conical flask was immediately titrated with a standard 0.01M EDTA solution, swirling continuously until the last reddish colour disappeared. The end-point was indicated by a clear blue colour.

Magnesium hardness concentration was determined using the formula below

$$\text{Mg}^{2+} \text{ (mg/dm}^3\text{)} = \frac{V_{\text{EDTA}} \times M_{\text{EDTA}} \times 1000 \times 24.32}{\text{cm}^3 \text{ of sample use}}$$

where

$$V_{\text{EDTA}} = \text{Titre Volume of EDTA used}$$

$$M_{\text{EDTA}} = \text{Molar Concentration of EDTA (0.01M)}$$

$$24.32 = \text{Molar Mass of Mg}^{2+}$$

$$1000 = \text{Conversion to mg/dm}^3$$

Determination of Dissolved Oxygen

Mine pond water sample was collected at a depth of about 1meter from the surface of the pond water body into a 250 cm³ narrow neck bottle, which was filled and stopper replaced under water. The collected water sample were fixed immediately with 2 cm³ of manganese iv oxide (MnSO₄) and 2cm³ alkaline iodide sodium azide reagents. The mixture was re-stopped and gently shaken. In the laboratory, 2 cm³ of conc. H₂SO₄ acid was added to the fixed sample by allowing the acid to run down the neck of the bottle.

The bottle was re-stopped and mixed gently until a homogenous deep-yellow solution resulted. Then 200 cm³ of the solution was withdrawn and transferred into a conical flask and was titrated against 0.025M sodium thiosulphate till the solution became pale yellow. 1cm³ of 1% starch solution was added at this point and a dark blue coloured solution was observed. The titration continued until the blue colour first disappeared. After the titration the dissolved oxygen was calculated and recorded as the volume of sodium thiosulphate used from the beginning of the titration to the end-point of the titration. This was registered in mg/dm³ as the concentration of dissolved oxygen in the water.

Dissolved oxygen was determined using the formula below

$$DO = \frac{V_{S_2O_3^{-2}} \times M \times 8 \times 100}{\text{Volume of sample}}$$

where

$V_{S_2O_3^{-2}}$ = volume of sodium thiosulphate ($Na_2S_2O_3$) used in the titration.

M = Molarity of $Na_2S_2O_3$ (0.025M).

8 = Atomic number of oxygen.

1000 = was the volume conversion per dm^3 .

Volume of sample = $100cm^3$ of mine-pond water.

Determination of Biological Oxygen Demand

Mine-pond water sample was collected at a depth below the surface of the pond water body into a 250 cm^3 narrow neck bottle, which was filled to capacity and stopped below the surface of water, the samples were wrapped with aluminium foil sheets and was incubated by keeping it in a dark place for five days (5 days) in the laboratory. The samples were then fixed with 2 cm of $MnSO_4$ and $2cm^3$ alkaline-iodide sodium azide reagents. 2 cm^3 of conc. H_2SO_4 was added into the incubated sample by allowing the acid to run down the neck of the bottle. The bottle was re-stoppered and mixed gently until a homogenous deep-yellow solution was observed. 100 cm^3 of the solution was withdrawn and transferred into a conical flask and was titrated against 0.025M sodium thiosulphate till it became pale yellow. 1 cm^3 of 1% starch solution was added and a dark-blue colour was observed. The titration continued until the blue colour first disappeared. After the titration, the biochemical oxygen demand was calculated and recorded as the volume of sodium thiosulphate used from the beginning to the end of the titration.

Biological Oxygen Demand was determined using the formula below

The value of biological oxygen demand was determined by subtracting the value of titration of BOD from the value of dissolved oxygen of the first day (DO_1) to give BOD

$$BOD = DO_{1\text{day}} - DO_{5\text{days}}$$

Determination of Sulphate

Sulphate was precipitated in dilute hydrochloric acid medium 2 molar as barium sulphate by the addition of barium chloride solution.

The barium sulphate was insoluble in the solution, because of this it was washed with water after filtration and dried to constant weight at 105 °C in an oven.

To 50 cm³ of mine pond sample was added 5cm³ of 2M HCl in drops 5 cm³ of it was boiled and barium chloride solution was added until all the sulphate was precipitated. The precipitate was filtered through glass sintered crucible and was dried in the oven at 105 °C to a constant weight. The weight of the precipitate alone was obtained by the difference between the crucible and precipitate, less the weight of empty crucible alone.

Sulphate was determined using the formula below

$$\text{SO}_4 \text{ mg/dm}^3 = \frac{\text{wt. BaSO}_4 \times 114.5 \times 1000}{\text{Ml. of Sample}}$$

Sulphate was precipitated in dilute 2 molar hydrochloric acid as barium sulphate by the addition of barium chloride solution.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

SPSS (2021), IBM Data Editor stat. 24 and python 3 Programming Language were used as the software for statistical analysis. The statistical analysis was based on the calculation of central tendencies of data example mean, standard deviation, variance, center point, range, minimum and maximum data measured and correlation co-efficient (r). Karl Pearson's coefficient of correlation (r) equation was used for quantitative measurement between two or more variable data.

RESULTS

The physicochemical parameters of the respective mine ponds (Gurum, Haske and Zawan) were presented in Tables 1–3. The physicochemical parameters are considered as one of the essential features that influence the mine ponds environment and have shown temporal difference. All the physicochemical parameters showed clear seasonal patterns which are very typical of tropical mine pond environment. It displayed different characteristics with seasons (dry and rainy) and showed continuous changes, relying on climatic and seasonal changes.

Table 1: Physico-chemical parameters of Gurum mine pond.

Parameters	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Mean	WHO(2006)
Water temp.(⁰ C)	22.10	22.50	22.50	22.60	22.50	22.00	20.30	22.50	21.80	22.00	20.30	20.00	21.76	30 ⁰ C
Colour (Hz Unit)	7.20	6.50	6.50	6.00	6.20	6.50	6.80	7.20	7.50	7.60	7.50	7.20	6.89	15Hz
pH	7.20	7.10	6.80	7.20	7.21	7.21	7.30	7.30	7.12	7.13	7.13	7.20	7.16	6.50 – 8.50
EC (µs/cm)	264.0	278.0	294.0	320.0	335.0	345.0	364.0	423.0	432.0	291.0	283.0	272.0	325.08	1200µs/cm
TDS (mg/dm ³)	169.0	284.0	311.0	349.0	458.0	561.0	597.0	566.0	563.0	455.0	345.0	284.0	411.83	1500mg/dm ³
Acidity(mg/dm ³)	15.20	20.30	35.00	30.00	25.00	23.00	22.10	22.30	21.30	21.50	20.40	20.10	23.02	-
Turbidity(NTU)	16.20	12.40	8.30	15.75	18.24	22.32	24.22	25.32	25.41	25.43	24.06	18.31	19.66	5NTU
Total alkalinity (mg/dm ³)	53.00	68.00	62.00	73.00	78.00	78.50	80.00	84.00	85.00	83.90	80.20	83.00	75.72	100mg/dm ³
Free CO ₂ (mg/dm ³)	4.20	4.50	3.20	3.30	4.40	6.40	6.60	6.80	6.82	6.50	5.60	5.00	5.28	-
D.O (mg/dm ³)	6.70	6.85	7.30	7.60	8.20	8.50	8.65	9.20	8.70	9.50	10.00	13.20	8.70	8-10mg/dm ³
B.O.D (mg/dm ³)	1.80	1.10	1.86	1.86	1.73	1.73	1.64	2.30	2.10	2.25	2.16	2.00	1.88	-
Chloride(mg/dm ³)	35.55	35.85	36.04	26.58	24.50	22.03	23.60	22.32	24.00	20.00	24.20	24.60	26.61	250mg/dm ³
Sulphate(mg/dm ³)	25.00	24.50	24.03	28.00	38.20	38.40	40.00	38.50	42.30	45.00	56.00	30.50	35.87	500mg/dm ³
Phosphate(mg/dm ³)	0.93	0.86	0.85	0.86	0.91	1.02	1.05	1.05	1.00	1.07	1.70	1.00	1.03	5mg/dm ³
Nitrate (mg/dm ³)	6.40	6.28	6.10	6.45	6.70	6.65	7.03	7.10	7.30	7.00	7.20	6.70	6.74	50mg/dm ³
Calcium (mg/dm ³)	32.40	44.10	32.20	112.0	104.7	58.60	58.80	45.30	43.20	37.10	35.50	31.07	52.91	75mg/dm ³
Magnesium(mg/dm ³)	2.42	2.82	3.22	3.40	5.20	5.35	6.35	6.36	7.42	7.20	7.10	6.42	5.27	20mg/dm ³
Total hardness (mg/dm ³)	120.0	98.75	144.3	146.0	160.2	123.8	165.3	154.0	138.0	135.1	128.7	125.2	136.61	500mg/dm ³

n=12

Table 2: Physico-chemical parameters of Haske mine pond.

Parameters	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Mean	WHO(2006)
Water temp.(⁰ C)	19.50	20.60	21.00	21.20	21.50	22.30	22.20	21.60	22.10	22.00	22.60	20.50	21.43	30 ⁰ C
Colour(Hz unit)	6.00	6.00	6.40	6.20	6.50	6.50	6.50	6.50	6.50	6.50	6.50	6.10	6.35	15Hz
pH	7.20	7.20	6.80	7.30	7.30	7.20	7.20	7.30	7.30	7.40	7.40	7.13	7.23	6.50-8.50
EC (μ s/cm)	173.0	184.0	225.0	235.0	245.0	255.0	275.0	306.0	321.0	292.0	220.0	175.0	242.17	1200 μ s/cm
TDS (mg/dm ³)	183.0	222.0	220.0	225.0	255.0	264.0	320.0	410.0	422.0	385.0	255.0	185.0	278.83	1500mg/dm ³
Acidity (mg/dm ³)	12.00	6.03	5.42	6.04	5.24	5.27	6.06	12.13	14.00	14.70	12.10	11.08	9.17	-
Turbidity(NTU)	11.20	15.50	12.70	18.20	21.80	22.20	24.03	25.10	25.32	24.21	18.14	16.24	19.55	5NTU
Total alkalinity (mg/dm ³)	30.20	30.10	30.04	30.20	35.04	65.70	64.50	42.03	37.08	35.30	32.70	29.50	38.53	100mg/dm ³
Free CO ₂ (mg/dm ³)	3.70	3.40	3.80	3.50	3.80	4.00	4.20	4.40	4.30	4.50	4.80	4.20	4.05	-
D.O (mg/dm ³)	6.90	7.20	7.40	8.00	8.50	8.30	9.00	9.40	9.50	10.00	10.20	13.10	8.96	8-10mg/dm ³
B.O.D (mg/dm ³)	2.30	2.30	2.50	2.10	3.20	3.20	3.20	3.30	3.40	4.10	4.30	4.50	3.20	-
Chloride (mg/dm ³)	35.85	35.87	36.02	26.75	24.60	20.20	23.60	22.60	24.30	26.00	28.10	29.00	27.74	250mg/dm ³
Sulphate(mg/dm ³)	15.00	19.90	23.40	26.02	34.00	38.03	39.04	40.00	38.50	41.00	42.10	34.02	32.58	500mg/dm ³
Phosphate (mg/dm ³)	2.16	2.15	1.80	2.10	2.26	3.30	3.60	3.31	3.50	3.52	3.10	2.40	2.77	5mg/dm ³
Nitrate (mg/dm ³)	6.50	6.48	6.45	6.70	6.65	6.65	7.02	7.10	7.30	7.50	7.20	6.70	6.85	50mg/dm ³
Calcium (mg/dm ³)	5.61	5.62	4.81	5.62	5.64	6.21	7.21	8.81	8.90	10.42	11.20	9.10	7.43	75mg/dm ³
Magnesium(mg/dm ³)	2.43	2.91	3.24	3.40	5.20	5.35	6.35	6.32	6.36	7.20	7.10	6.32	5.18	20mg/dm ³
Totalhardness(mg/dm ³)	230.0	250.0	235.0	240.0	250.0	295.0	298.7	280.0	270.6	250.0	240.4	237.0	256.39	500mg/dm ³

n=12

Table 3: Physico-chemical parameters of Zawan mine pond.

Parameters	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Mean	WHO (2006)
Watertemp.(⁰ C)	21.5	22	23	23	22.5	22.1	20.3	22.5	22.3	22.5	22.3	20.3	22.03	30 ⁰ C
Colour(Hz unit)	6.2	6.2	6.0	6.4	6.4	6.5	6.5	6.5	6.8	7.2	6.8	6.5	6.50	15Hz
pH	7.3	7.3	7.1	7.4	7.4	7.4	7.5	7.3	7.4	7.4	7.3	7.3	7.34	6.50-8.50
EC (μ s/cm)	264.0	265.0	321.0	343.0	348.0	365.0	393.0	398.0	345.0	342.0	292.0	275.0	329.25	1200 μ s/cm
TDS (mg/dm ³)	225.0	245.0	255.0	264.0	320.0	430.0	435.0	385.0	288.0	256.0	245.0	220.0	297.33	1500mg/dm ³
Acidity (mg/dm ³)	7.30	11.00	12.00	6.30	5.60	5.35	5.30	5.10	5.00	4.30	4.35	5.42	6.42	-
Turbidity(NTU)	13.00	12.20	11.31	16.02	18.10	18.50	20.00	19.50	22.12	21.02	18.30	16.02	17.17	5NTU
Total alkalinity (mg/dm ³)	24.50	24.30	24.00	25.01	30.07	37.30	55.40	54.05	45.90	45.40	37.30	25.80	35.75	100mg/dm ³
Free CO ₂ (mg/dm ³)	2.3	3.4	3.7	3.8	4.0	4.1	4.3	4.5	3.8	4.2	4.1	4.2	3.87	-
D.O (mg/dm ³)	7.10	6.90	6.40	7.50	8.00	8.50	7.60	9.00	9.50	9.80	10.12	13.20	8.64	8-10 mg/dm ³
B.O.D (mg/dm ³)	3.2	3.0	3.4	3.5	3.7	3.2	4.0	4.2	4.3	4.3	4.5	4.5	3.82	-
Chloride (mg/dm ³)	22.69	26.02	35.78	21.3	20.15	19.51	18.30	19.00	17.21	18.73	20.02	21.54	21.69	250mg/dm ³
Sulphate(mg/dm ³)	12.00	11.30	14.40	13.28	12.70	14.50	18.40	20.02	22.03	24.00	25.00	26.00	17.80	500mg/dm ³
Phosphate (mg/dm ³)	0.64	0.68	0.66	0.59	0.95	1.24	1.26	1.30	1.28	1.40	1.62	1.77	1.12	5mg/dm ³
Nitrate (mg/dm ³)	6.50	6.48	6.45	6.70	6.85	7.10	7.30	7.50	7.20	7.02	6.70	6.65	6.87	50mg/dm ³
Calcium (mg/dm ³)	6.50	6.30	6.22	7.30	7.50	8.40	8.90	7.46	9.30	9.30	9.10	6.50	7.73	75mg/dm ³
Magnesium (mg/dm ³)	7.2	9.5	6.5	10.4	12.8	6.2	17.1	16.5	17.2	19	20.1	18.3	13.40	20mg/dm ³
Total hardness(mg/dm ³)	190.0	194.8	220.5	225.2	235.4	265.0	281.3	255.9	254.5	234.3	210.0	195.6	230.2	500mg/dm ³

n=12

DISCUSSIONS

The physicochemical parameters of the respective mine ponds (Gurum, Haske and Zawan) were presented in Tables 1 - 3. The physicochemical parameters are considered as one of the essential features that influence the mine ponds environment and have shown temporal difference. All the physicochemical parameters showed clear seasonal patterns which are

very typical of tropical mine pond environment. It displayed different characteristics with seasons (dry and rainy) and showed continuous changes, relying on climatic and seasonal changes.

The temperature was maximum during the dry season and low during the rainy season. However the parameters fluctuated, few changes were observed in metals and ions as the pH changes and the pattern was during dry and rainy season. The water temperature was measured with a mercury in glass thermometer and the temperature variation was influenced by weather conditions such as air temperature, humidity, wind and sun energy, it also varied seasonally. Gurum temperature ranges from 22.10-22.60⁰C during the dry season, and 20.30-22.50⁰C during the rainy season. During dry season, Haske temperature 19.50 to 21.2 during the dry season and 21.5-22.6⁰C during the rainy season. The Zawan temperature ranges from 21.5 – 23.0⁰C during the dry season and 20.3-22.5⁰C during the rainy season. This was in line with the report of,^[19] that water temperature was low during the harmattan period of the year in their study of some water bodies in Northern Nigeria. This findings was in accordance with observations of.^[20] This result was within the permissible limit of^[21] standard of 30⁰C.

pH: the pH of the mine ponds at Gurum ranges from 6.8-7.2 during the dry season and 7.21-7.3 during the raining season. pH of Haske ranges from 7.2-7.3 during dry season and ranged from 7.2-7.4 during rainy season. Zawan pH ranges from 7.1-7.4 during dry season and 7.3-7.5 during rainy season. The increase in the rainy season was due to influx of flood that washed the surrounding surface materials into the pond and the soil being clayey in nature tend to increase the alkalinity of the water. The dry season pH decreased towards the acidic region due to evaporation and concentration of the ions in the ponds.

The pH range obtained falls within the recommended range of (pH 6.5 - 9) by^[22] which supports aquatic life including fish. This result is in accordance with the report by^[23] that the levels of pH are closely related to the amount of carbonates and ions present in solution. Similar observation was made by.^[24] This condition could be due to the alkaline nature of the top soil which was clay, loamy and sedimentary in nature. The result falls within^[21] standard limit of pH 6.5 - 8.5, this showed the pH of mine pond water in dry and rainy season.

Conductivity is an indication of total dissolved solids (TDS) both for metals, organic and inorganic found in the ponds. The Gurum pond samples ranges from 320-294 during dry season and 335-432 during the rainy season. That of Haske ranges from 173-235 for dry

season and 175-321 during rainy season. Zawan samples ranges from 264-343 during dry season and 275-398 during rainy season. This was within the^[21] guideline value of 1,200 μ s/cm. This observation was in line with^[21] who reported increase in conductivity during the rainy season. The values determined were within the^[21] standard of 1200 μ s/cm which indicates moderate dissolved solids in the ponds.

Total dissolved solids (TDS): this is an indication of the degree of dissolved substances such as metals, organic and inorganic materials and ions in the water. The Gurum samples ranges from 196-349 during the dry season and 458-597 during the rainy season. Samples for Haske ranges from 183-225 during dry season and 255-422 during rainy season. Zawan samples ranges from 225-264 during dry season and 320-385 during rainy season. The increase in value during rainy season was due to the washing of the surface soil into the pond which are mostly calcium-carbonate. The values of TDS determined were within the^[21] permissible standard of 1500 mg/dm³.

Dissolved oxygen: the dissolved oxygen content was determined by Winkler's method. Dissolved oxygen plays an important role in aquatic environment and is essential for the growth of microorganisms and fish production. The dissolved oxygen is governed by the water turbulence, surface diffusion, rate of photosynthesis, BOD, water temperature and CO₂ concentration in the ponds. The samples for Gurum pond ranges from 6.7-7.6 during dry season and 8.2-13.20 in rainy season. The samples for Haske ranged from 6.9-8.0 during dry season and 8.3-13.1 in rainy season while for Zawan, sample ranges from 6.4 - 7.5 during dry season and 7.6-13.2 during rainy season. This findings agrees with^[25] who reported that dissolved oxygen concentration was high during the harmattan period. The highest values recorded were above the^[21] standard of (8-10 mg/dm³).

BOD is a measure of oxygen required by microbes to degrade the organic matter under aerobic condition. It increases with influx of domestic waste and organic materials in the ponds. It is lower during dry season and more during rainy season. Samples for Gurum ranges from 1.10-1.86 during dry season and 1.64-2.3 during rainy season. Samples for Haske ranges from 2.10-2.50 during dry season and 3.20-4.5 during the rainy season. Samples for Zawan ranges from 3.0-3.5 during dry season and 3.2-4.5 during rainy season.

Turbidity is associated with the possibility of microbiological contamination. The Gurum ponds experienced turbidity which ranged from 12.40 - 16.20 during the dry season and

22.32-25.43 during rainy season. Haske pond ranges from 11.20-18.20 during dry season and 21.8-25.32 during rainy season. Zawan pond ranges from 11.31-16.02 during dry season and 18.10-22.12 during rainy season.

CONCLUSION

The physicochemical parameters of the mine ponds have been analysed and their concentrations known as in Tables 1, 2 and 3. The study showed that the physicochemical parameters of the ponds are favorable for the survival of catfish, since the fishes survived as experimental fish farmed in the ponds for over seven months. In conclusion, the ponds are suitable for the survival of fish, since experimental fish was farmed in the respective ponds and they survived.

RECOMMENDATION

Washing of cars and dumping of refuse near the ponds should be stopped considering that some of the ponds are used as domestic source of water for the community and the habitat for fish.

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